

GROWING SIBERIAN STURGEON (*Acipenser baerii*) IN FLOW THROUGH SYSTEM IN CONDITION OF THE UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article presents the results of studies on breeding Siberian sturgeon (*Acipenser baerii*) fish in flow through system at the experimental base of the Fisheries Scientific Research Institute.

Keywords: Siberian sturgeon, stocking density, flow through system, intensive technology.

Аннотация. Мазкур мақолада Балиқчилик илмий-тадқиқот институтининг тажриба базасида ўстириляётган сибир осетр (*Acipenser baerii*) балиқларни оқар сув бассейнларида тури тигизликда етиштириши бўйича олиб борилган тадқиқотлар натижалари келтирилган.

Аннотация. В статье представлены результаты исследований по разведению сибирского осетра (*Acipenser baerii*) в проточных бассейнах на экспериментальной базе Научно-исследовательского института рыбоводства.

In modern conditions, commercial sturgeon farming is developing in the world to supply the consumer market with valuable delicacy products. Uzbekistan has favorable conditions for the development of aquaculture in general and sturgeon breeding in particular. Therefore, in the strategy of socio-economic development of the country, the fish industry is designated as a key sector of the economy. One of the most notable objects of aquaculture today are various species of sturgeon fish and, in particular, the Siberian sturgeon. The most important advantage of the sturgeon is its ability to adapt well to environmental factors, especially water temperature and salinity. It is this feature that makes it possible to breed it in many places in the world that are not its natural habitat.

Sturgeon breeding in the country has only recently begun to develop and therefore faces many technical difficulties: breeding technologies are still at the testing stage, especially the stages of feeding, sexual maturation, stimulation of artificial reproduction, egg production and incubation, which are the most important.

The performed research on the state of temperature and hydrochemical regimes in flow through system during the period of the experiment showed that they met the requirements for sturgeon fish farming. In the flow through system (10 m³) the temperature was within 19-25 °C, the average value was 20.7-24.5 °C, the difference between morning and evening temperatures did not exceed 3°C. The hydrochemical regime indicators were within acceptable limits (Table 1): pH 7,5, dissolved oxygen content 6,3-6,7 mg/l, nitrogenous compounds N-NH₄⁺ 0.17-0.23, N-NO₂ - 0.02-0.04, and N-NO₃ - 0.16-0.22 and tended to increase at higher stocking densities, however, these values were within acceptable limits for the stage of commercial sturgeon breeding. Water quality, in general, was maintained at an optimal level, water flow rate was 5 m³/h.

Parameters of fish habitat in the basin during the experiment

Table 1

Parameters	Stocking density		
	15 pieces /m ²	25 pieces m ²	35 pieces /m ²
Average temperature, °C	24,8 ± 0,5	24,8 ± 0,5	24,8 ± 0,5

pH	7,4 ± 0,02	7,4 ± 0,03	7,4 ± 0,03
Dissolved oxygen content (mg/l)	7,1 ± 0,08	6,7 ± 0,18	6,3 ± 0,15
N-NH ₄ ⁺ (mg/l)	0,17 ± 0,03	0,21 ± 0,02	0,25 ± 0,08
N-NO ₂ (mg/l)	0,02 ± 0,01	0,02 ± 0,01	0,04 ± 0,03
N-NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/l)	0,18 ± 0,06	0,18 ± 0,08	0,20 ± 0,05

The initial weight of Siberian sturgeon in the experiment when grown in flow through system in three variants was 810±5 g, after 3 months the final weight was in the range from 1430 to 1650 g (Table 2) at different stocking densities: 15, 25, 35 individual/m². The highest final weight (1650 g) was achieved at a stocking density of 15 pieces /m², the lowest (1430 g) – at 35 kg/m². The growth rates (SGR_w and AGR) were also higher at stocking densities of 15 and 25 kg/m² than at a stocking density of 35 kg/m²; however, there was no statistically significant difference between the indicators at stocking 15 and 25 kg/m² (P > 0.05).

Parameters	Stocking density		
	15 pieces/m ²	25 pieces/m ²	35 pieces/m ²
Initial weight (g)	810,0 ± 0,53	810,0 ± 0,39	810,0 ± 0,41
Final weight (g)	1650 ± 123	1630 ± 125	1430 ± 119
SGR _w (%/day)	0,79 ± 0,02	0,78 ± 0,01	0,62 ± 0,02
AGR (g/day)	9,3 ± 0,35	9,1 ± 0,39	6,8 ± 0,35
Fish productivity (kg/m ²)	19,8 ± 0,29	32,6 ± 0,97	34,3 ± 0,46
Biomass yield (kg/tank, 9,4 m ³)	196,5 ± 3,1	322,7 ± 4,2	339,5 ± 2,8
FCR	1,5 ± 0,08	1,5 ± 0,05	1,9 ± 0,13
SR (%)	80,0	80,0	74,3

The feed conversion ratio (FCR) and survival rate (SR) were also better at lower stocking densities (15 and 25 pieces /m²) compared to higher stocking density (35 pieces /m²) (1.6 vs. 2.0; P < 0.05). There was no statistically significant difference in FCR and survival rate between stocking density of 15 and 25 pieces /m² (P > 0.05). This experiment shows that stocking density up to 25 individual/m² is optimal for commercial sturgeon culture in flow through system for economically and technically efficient fish farming, while ensuring good fish growth rate.

Stocking density is one of the factors that has a great influence on the growth rate of fish in captivity and has been observed in many groups of captive species (Yi et al., 1996; Hengswat et al., 1997). Generally, increasing stocking density has a negative effect on growth performance as well as on the interactions between fish in the same group: competition for food and living space, increased stress and physical collisions, sensitivity to pathogens lead to a decrease in immunity, feed efficiency, and survival rate (Holm et al., 1990; Haylor, 1991; Miao, 1992; Huang and Chiu, 1997; Canario et al., 1998; Irwin et al., 1999; Silva et al., 2000; Baldwin, 2010). However, the effect of stocking density on fish production depends on many factors, such as species composition, heredity, and developmental stage in correlation with the culture system. In addition, the management of the system itself also has a strong influence on the culture results - these are factors such as feed supply, environmental conditions, oxygen regime, water changes, and disease prevention measures. Stocking density is a factor determining the economic and technical efficiency of a culture system and should always be considered and optimized, especially in intensive aquaculture systems (Papst et al., 1992).

Many studies have been conducted on the effect of stocking density on sturgeon. A study on the effect of stocking density on *A. oxyrinchus* sturgeon at densities of 1.27, 2.49, and 3.80

kg/m² by Mirosław et al. (2011) showed that stocking density significantly affected the growth rate and FCR of the fish, with the lower the density, the higher the growth rate and feed efficiency. Similarly, the work of Andrei et al. (2016) on the rearing of hybrid sturgeon (*H. huso x A. ruthenus*) showed that densities of 3.19–14.95 kg/m³ also affected the growth rate and survival rate, with the general trend being that the higher the stocking density, the lower the growth rate and the higher the survival rate. More detailed studies by Dicu et al. (2013), Li et al. (2012) and Ni et al. (2014) showed that density affects not only growth but also biochemical and hematological parameters of sturgeons. In the species *A. stellatus* at a density of 18.7–28.6 kg/m³; the species *A. schrenckii*, at stocking densities of 3.7, 6.9 and 9.3 kg/m³ and 0.3–1.8 kg/m², these authors noted a significant effect on the growth rate, some biochemical parameters, but did not notice an effect on the percentage of fish survival. An effect on the feed conversion ratio was noted in the study of Li et al. (2012), but not noticed in the study of Ni et al. (2014). A similar trend was also noted by Yang et al. (2011) on the sturgeon species *A. schrenckii* at the fry stage at a stocking density of 120–600 individuals/m³, cultured in cement tanks, and at the commercial stage at 3.0–7.5 individuals/m², cultured in earthen ponds.

However, a study of the effect of stocking densities of 6, 9, 12, 15 and 18 individuals/m² on Siberian sturgeons (*A. baerii*) weighing from 460 g/individual in a recirculating tank system (500 l/tank) by Zaze et al. (2009) showed that there was no difference in growth performance and FCR between the different experimental densities. At the stage of 0.5–1.0 kg/individual, according to Steffens et al. (1990) this species can be cultured in a recirculating tank system at high stocking density of about 25 kg/m². Hasanlipour et al. (2013) also noted that high stocking density (24–72 individuals/m³, weight 600 g/individual) of this sturgeon species does not affect biochemical parameters. Overall, all these authors concluded that Siberian sturgeon can be cultured at very high stocking densities, especially in RAS (recirculating aquaculture systems).

As a result of the conducted research, it can be said that growing Siberian sturgeon fish in flow through system in the conditions of our country will give good results. In this case, it is necessary to constantly check the hydrochemical condition of the water and feed the fish with quality feed.

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